

Titanium(IV) Complexes of Aryl Hydroxamic Acids at Different Acidities—A Comparative Study.

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Benzo-, salicyl-, cinnamo-, phenylacetyl hydroxamic acids and their N-substituted phenyl derivatives are found to form yellow coloured complexes with titanium of varied compositions at different acid concentrations and in different solvent mediums. The complexes, formed with hydroxamic acids, are extractable into isoamyl alcohol, but not into chloroform; whereas the complexes, formed with N-phenyl substituted hydroxamic acids, are extractable into both isoamyl alcohol and chloroform with lesser intensity in the former solvent. Spectrophotometric studies have shown the existence of complexes with high ligand to metal ratios at lower acidities in case of titanium hydroxamic acid complexes. Exact reverse trend was observed among titanium complex of N-phenyl substituted hydroxamic acids except N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine. Extended Yatsimirskii's, Leden's and Harvey-Manning's methods were applied to evaluate stepwise and overall formation constants, of different complexes. For some constants an electronic computer (IBM 1130) was deployed using FORTRAN Programming.

AFTER the introduction of the reagent, N-Benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine, by Shome¹ for gravimetric determination of various metals, P. Ray and his co-workers^{2, 3} undertook the study of feasibility of salicylhydroxamic acid as an analytical reagent for different transition metals. Since then review articles^{4, 5} and monographs^{6, 7} have well documented the distinctive role of different aryl hydroxamic acids and their N-phenyl analogues as useful analytical reagents for various kinds of metals. A very few pieces of works^{2, 3, 8-13} have also paid attention to formation of complexes of variable compositions at varied acidities. This paper presents a comparative account of different features of titanium(IV) complexes, through extractive spectrophotometric measurements at various acidities, formed with the following pairs of the reagents: benzohydroxamic acid (BHA) and N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NBPHA), salicyl hydroxamic acid (SHA) and N-salicyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NSPHA), cinnamohydroxamic acid (CHA) and N-cinnamoyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NCPHA), phenylacetyl hydroxamic acid (PacHA) and N-phenylacetyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NPacPHA). Job's and molar ratio methods are applied to find the compositions of the yellow coloured complexes formed with these selected pairs of reagents at different acidity ranges. The stability constants of different systems have been calculated following extended Yatsimirskii's^{1, 4}, Leden's^{1, 5} and Harvey-Manning's^{1, 6} methods. The comparative suitability of the reagents for extractive photometric determination of trace amounts of titanium has been discussed.

Experimental

Reagents and solutions: A stock solution of titanium (2.18 mg/ml) was prepared from A. R. grade potassium titanyl oxalate and standardised¹⁷. Metal solutions of desired strengths for different sets of experiments were obtained after proper dilution of the stock

solution with twice distilled water. Aryl hydroxamic acids and the corresponding N-substituted phenyl derivatives were prepared following the method of Blatt^{1, 2} and Shome¹ respectively. Standard reagent solutions of various strengths were made by dissolving the required amount of the former substances in isoamyl alcohol (A.R.) and those of latter in chloroform (A.R.). Other chemicals used in all spectrophotometric measurements were of A.R. or spectrograde quality.

Apparatus: A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with matched 1.0 cm glass cells was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

A Cambridge Bench pH meter was used to record the pH of the solutions.

A scientific and electronic computer (IBM 1130) using FORTRAN Programming was employed for evaluation of the formation constants of 1 : 3 systems^{1, 9}.

Extraction procedure: An aliquot of titanium solution ($8.352 \times 10^{-3} M$) was taken in a 50 ml beaker and adjusted to desired acidity, and finally transferred into a 100 ml separatory funnel. A desired amount of reagent solution either in isoamyl alcohol or chloroform was added to 15 ml of aqueous phase. The volume of nonaqueous phase was maintained equal to that of the aqueous phase in all the cases. After shaking thoroughly the two phases for 10-15 minutes to reach equilibrium, the yellow coloured nonaqueous layer was drained out over anhydrous sodium sulphate in a 50 ml beaker. The process was repeated with a 5 ml portion of the chosen solvent. The combined extract, after being dried over, was diluted to 25 ml with the solvent in a volumetric flask. The absorbances of the solutions were measured at suitable wavelengths.

Results and Discussions

Reactions of Ti(IV) with the selected pairs of reagents, mentioned earlier, have shown that the formation of complexes with high ligand to metal ratios are favoured at lower acidities and those of lower ratios at higher acidities with hydroxamic acids. The exact reverse trend is observed among Ti-complexes with N-phenyl substituted hydroxamic acids, except in case of NBPFA complexes. Moreover, the complexes, formed with the former class of reagents, are extractable into isoamyl alcohol, but not into chloroform. While the complexes, formed with the latter series, are extractable both into chloroform and isoamyl alcohol with lesser intensity in the latter solvent. The molar absorptivity values are found to increase with increasing acidity. The molar absorptivity values of titanium complexes of N-phenyl substituted analogues are higher than those of hydroxamic acids. In all the cases, commonly associated ions have tolerable effect on absorbance measurements. The ions which generally interfere include Fe(III), V(V), Mo(VI), Cr(VI), W(VI), U(IV) and U(VI). Among them, the effect of Fe(III) and V(V) are most prominent at higher acidities and those of Mo(VI) and U(IV) in lower acidities. The values of molar absorptivity and sensitivity, calculated from Beer's law data along the values of the formation constants are compiled in Table 1.

All the hydroxamic acids and only NCPFA form 1 : 1 complexes. Complexes of CHA and NCPFA are found to have absorption maximum at 360 and 410 nm respectively; others have no λ_{max} . The molar absorptivity is found to be highest with SHA, formed in 50% ethanol medium. The sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complexes can be arranged in the order: SHA > CHA > BHA > NCPFA > PacHA. The stability constants of the complexes are found to follow the order: SHA > NCPFA > CHA > BHA > PacHA. The structures of the ligands suggest that intramolecular hydrogen bonding, feasible only in Ti-SHA complex, probably attributes to its highest stability while decreased inductive effect of >C=O group due to supply of electrons from nearby double bond results in increased basicity of N atom of the ligand (compared to other ligands) and probably leads to improved stability of Ti-NCPFA complex. As the formulae of the isolated complexes^{20,21} suggest that titanium exists at TiO^{2+} in the pH as well as normality range of acidity, the formula of 1 : 1 complexes is, in all probability, $[TiO RCl]$ where HR stands for the ligands.

All the hydroxamic acids and their N phenyl analogues form 1 : 2 complexes. The absorption maximum of SHA complex, formed in 50% ethanol medium, is at 360 nm; whereas NBPFA, CHA, NPacPHA and

TABLE 1

Composition	Reagent	Acidity range (HCl)	Molar absorptivity ($\times 10^{-3}$)	Sensitivity in μg per cm^2	Overall stability constant (log K) by Yatsimirskii's & Harvey-Manning's method
1 : 1	SHA	Over 2N	6.22 \pm 0.05	0.007	2.69
	CHA	7.5 - 9N	3.35 \pm 0.04	0.013	2.39
	BHA	Do	2.32 \pm 0.02	0.021	2.25
	NCPFA	pH 0.5 - 2.5N	1.66 \pm 0.02	0.029	2.51
	PacHA	7.5 - 9N	1.44	0.033	1.58
1 : 2	SHA	0.5 - 1.5N	5.95 \pm 0.03	0.0080	5.00
	NCPFA	3 - 5N	5.27 \pm 0.04	0.0095	5.36
	NBPFA	9 - 11N	3.95 \pm 0.04	0.0120	7.42 ^a
	CHA	2 - 4.5N	3.33 \pm 0.11	0.0150	4.59
	NSPHA	2 - 5N	1.90 \pm 0.04	0.0250	4.72
	NPacPHA	1 - 3N	1.84 \pm 0.01	0.0260	3.68
	BHA	2 - 4N	1.48 \pm 0.03	0.0300	4.43
PacHA	5 - 6.5N	1.24 \pm 0.01	0.0400	4.29	
1 : 3	NCPFA	7.5 - 9N	9.82 \pm 0.06	0.003	12.73
	CHA	pH 0.8 - 1.4	2.63 \pm 0.01	0.020	7.92
	NPacPHA	4 - 7N	2.18 \pm 0.02	0.020	6.92
	NSPHA	7.5 - 9N	1.89 \pm 0.02	0.021	6.69
	PacHA	3 - 4.5	0.889 \pm 0.008	0.054	5.78
1 : 4	SHA	pH 0.8 - 1.5	4.31	0.017	9.46
	NBPFA	2 - 5N	3.20	0.014	8.41 ^b
	NPacPHA	7.5 - 9N	3.20	0.015	12.63
	PacHA	1 - 2.5N	0.889 \pm 0.008	0.054	7.19

a. $\log K_1 = 3.84$, $\log K_2 = 3.58$

b. $\log K_1 = 0.78$, $\log K_2 = 2.15$, $\log K_3 = 2.67$, $\log K_4 = 2.82$

NCPHA complexes absorb maximum at 380, 390 and 400 nm respectively. Others do not have absorption maximum in the visible region. The sensitivity and molar absorptivity of the complexes are in the order: SHA > NCPHA > NBPCHA > CHA > NSPHA \approx NPacPHA > BHA > PacHA. The overall stability constant values of the complexes can be arranged in the order: NBPCHA > NCPCHA > SHA > NSPHA > CHA > BHA > PacHA > NPacPHA. Among the 1:2 complexes, formed at 4N HCl, the value of the stability constant is found to be the highest with NCPCHA complex. This may be attributed to increased basicity of N atom in NCPCHA, as suggested earlier. On the basis of data of stability constants and preceding information, the formula for 1:2 complexes except Ti-NBPCHA complex may be represented as $[\text{TiOR}_2]$ where HR stands for the ligands.

Among the 1:3 complexes, Ti-CHA is formed in pH range and others are formed at normality range of acidity. It is found from absorption spectra that NSPHA and NPacPHA complexes absorb maximum at 370 nm and that of NCPCHA at 400 nm. The molar absorptivity values of the complexes follow the order: NCPCHA > CHA > NPacPHA > NSPHA > PacHA. The Sandell's sensitivity of the complexes can be arranged as follows: NCPCHA > CHA \approx NPacPHA \approx NSPHA > PacHA. The values of the overall stability constants, calculated by different methods are arranged in the order: NCPCHA > CHA > NPacPHA > NSPHA > PacHA. The highest stability constant value and the lowest degree of dissociation (0.199) of Ti-NCPCHA complex may be attributed to increased basicity of N atom, as mentioned earlier. Leden's method of graphical extrapolation indicates the formation of 1:2 species for CHA, NCPCHA, PacHA and NPacPHA complexes as the first and second successive formation constants' values are obtained from the experimental plots; although Job's and molar ratio method indicate the formation of 1:3 complex and three stepwise constants are obtained by Yatsimirskii's method. This may be due to probable association of one of the ligand molecule from outer sphere of the coordination zone. The formulae of the complexes may be suggested to be $[\text{Ti}(\text{O}(\text{R})_2)_2] \text{RH}$ where RH stands for the ligands. For NSPHA complex, all the three stepwise constant values are obtained by both Yatsimirskii's and Leden's method with the order $K_3 > K_1 > K_2$. The formula for the complex is suggested to be $\text{H}^+ [\text{Ti}(\text{O}(\text{R})_2)_2 \text{RH}]^-$ where the first two ligands are attached to titanium as bidentate unit and the third one behaving as unidentate moiety. Moreover, there is probability of internal hydrogen bonding.

Among the 1:4 complexes, only Ti-SHA complex is formed at pH range, others being formed in the normality range of acidity. Only Ti-NBPCHA complex has absorption maximum at 360 nm. The others do not have absorption maximum in the visible region. The molar absorptivity, calculated from Beer's law data, appears to be the highest with SHA complex, then more or less of the same order for NBPCHA and NPacPHA complexes and the lowest for PacHA complex. The sensitivity of the complexes, except for

PacHA complex, appear more or less in the same order. The overall stability constants may be arranged as follows: NPacPHA > SHA > NBPCHA > PacHA. Leden's method of graphical extrapolation indicates the formation of 1:2 species for PacHA complex and 1:3 species for the other 1:4 complexes. Comparing the product of the first two stepwise constants by Leden's method with the overall stability constant value, calculated by Harvey-Manning's method, of PacHA complex, the formula is proposed to be $\text{RH}_2^+ [\text{Ti}(\text{O}(\text{R})_2)_2 \text{Cl}]^- \text{RH}$. The values of the stepwise constants for Ti-complexes are found to follow the order $K_4 > K_3 > K_2 > K_1$. The formula of the complex is proposed to be $\text{H}^+ [\text{Ti}(\text{O}(\text{R})_2)_2 \text{R}]^- \text{RH}$; RH stands for ligands.

Phenyl substituted parent compound, N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine (NBPCHA), has some unique properties which have led to deviations from the general trend of complex formations with other analogues mentioned earlier. NBPCHA forms a Ti-complex with metal to ligand ratio of 1:2 at 9-11N HCl medium. Formation of this at high acidity and the overall stability constant of this complex, $\log K$ of 7.42 ($\log K_1 = 3.84$, $\log K_2 = 3.58$) compared to constants of 1:2 complexes of other analogues suggest it to be structurally different from others. This complex is $[\text{TiR}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ where the titanyl oxygen has been replaced by two chlorine atoms in conformity with its formation at high acidity. $[\text{TiR}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ has also been isolated in the solid state²⁹. The 1:2 complex formed at pH 1-2 is found to have the structure $[\text{TiOR}_2]^{20}$. If we consider the properties of titanyl (oxygenated) complexes, then the formation of 1:4 complex at 2-5N HCl and of 1:2 complex at pH 1-2 will be in the general trend of formation of titanium complexes with aryl hydroxamic acids.

Judging the degree of dissociation, sensitivity, overall stability values and the amount of the reagent used, NCPCHA is found to be the most suitable reagent not only for detection, but also for extractive spectrophotometric estimation of titanium at 8N HCl as 1:3 complex to be followed by NPacPHA at 8N HCl as 1:4 complex. Other reagents, also when used in large quantities, may also be used as analytical reagents. Among them only SHA can be recommended for the same purpose for detection and estimation of small quantities of titanium at 1N and 5N HCl in ethanol-water medium (1:1).

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